

***Innovative Materials and Products – A development of a
“Smart Illuminative and object sensing sports and biking
jacket”***

written by

*Dhruv Ramani, Md. Salauddin Sikder, Md. Zulfikar Hasan,
Laura Juchem & Milena Blessin*

*Faculty of Textile- and Clothing Technology
Study course: MA Textile Trade and Technology
Hochschule Niederrhein – University of Applied Sciences,
Mönchengladbach*

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Supervised by Prof. Dr.-Ing. Alexander Büsgen

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1. The selected field

For the development of an innovative product the field of smart sport textiles was chosen, imagining that this product is developed in a company that is experienced in the production of sportsclothing and that has a high quality and nearly luxurious image to its customers. They already launched innovative products which became bestsellers like jackets that are made of a patented breathable fabric with antiseptical and skin friendly features.

Often smart textiles are used for increased convenience but for the project the focus will be on customer safety. Prerequisite for this decision is the issue of high number of deaths of bikers in bicycle traffic in the last months due to the overseeing of car or truck drivers.¹ Therefore it was planned to develop a product that would deal especially with those issues. The field in which the innovation is implemented is *smart safety bikerwear*. The product will be a piece of clothing, either jacket or trouser, that lights up because of the movement due to integrated glass fibers to minimize and eliminate the risk of being overseen. Moreover the product comprises an integrated sensor which is able to measure a minimum distance for approaching objects to provide a warning feature noise. It was planned, that the products are made out of synthetic fibers like Polyester, Nylon or Polyurethane that is typical and common for durable clothing and sportswear.²

The production method can be judged as being classical. The fabrics are woven and cutted, the pieces are sewn together and the technologies are added. Some seams might be sealed to increase weather resistance. Zippers and other additional items like elastics are added. There is no need for special methods like seamless fully fashion knitting. The products are purposed for increasing safety for bikers on the street but they can also be worn to other sportage occasions like hiking, walking the dog or other types of activities where an increased visibility is advantageous. Here the noise sensor simply can be shut off when it is not needed.

When it comes to the pricing of the pieces an above average price will be charged. Firstly, because in general high quality sports clothes are sold on a rather high price level due to its technical circumstances and effort.³ Secondly because of the added

¹ Cf. (online): Grobusch (2019).

² Cf. (online): Decathlon (2020).

³ Cf. (online): Sportcheck (2020).

smart features and therefore high material costs of the pieces as well as because of the luxurious image and reputation of the company that it is produced for. Lastly one can judge the market for such sports clothes as growing. Due to climate change, people tend to use more environment friendly means of transport. On the other hand, the growing number of accidents makes people to think more about how to increase safety when being in the traffic on a bike. Therefore the demand for such type of products is existing and moreover a growing potential can be expected.

2. The innovation

When it comes to the innovative products to be created, the decision will be made between a jacket and trousers. Both will be made of the same material and will have the same functions. The jacket is planned to have a nylon and glassfiber outer fabric and a fleece interlining. The trousers will be made out of the same material but without a fleece interlining.

Typically, fleece is produced from polyester and also can be made from recycled plastics, making it eco-friendly and inexpensive. For making fleece, fibers of polyester are woven into light fabric and brushed later to help fibers to increase in volume. The main characteristics of fleece is providing warmth and is therefore used to manufacture almost every heat protected clothing from ear-warmers for baby calves to underwear for astronauts. Fleece has a pile surface on both sides of the fabric, meaning the material can hold a bit more warmth. Not only it is warm and durable, but it is moisture resistant too, making it ideal for extreme weather conditions and for sportswear. It is also an ideal material for athletic garments as the cloth wicks perspiration and moisture away from the body, keeping athletes dry. Due to its versatility, it is most commonly used today.⁴

Nylon is a synthetic polymer of polyamides which is highly used in manufacturing most for the textiles of the sports industry. Nylon has an excellent strength and abrasion resistance with great stretch/elastic recovery. Additionally, it is durable, offers good resistance to sunlight and is resistant to heat and water. All mentioned properties with

⁴ Cf. (online): Luca (2018).

great wicking does make Nylon to a material of choice for sportswear fabrics. It is one of the most cost-effective and low maintenance options in textile industry.⁵

Optical glass fibers refer to the medium and the technology associated with the transmission of information in the form of light along glass fiber. The mechanism of transmission belongs to total internal reflection. Due to its total internal reflection, they are used for long distance and high-performance data networking.⁶

As we all know, increasing visibility reduces the danger of being overseen. Usually, for that purpose it is worked with reflectors that shine bright when being exposed to light sources. For this innovation, visibility is created by including glass fibers into the outer nylon fabric that lights up due to body movement. Therefore the clothing piece enlightens during the whole ride and not only when light hits the reflector like it is common with conventional reflectors. Furthermore a sensor will be included, that measures a minimum distance to cars and trucks driving besides the biker. Here a minimum distance of 1 meter will lead to a loud noise that warns the biker as well as the driver. The noise will come out of a speaker that is as well integrated to the piece of clothing. The lining of the jacket will be made out of soft polyester fleece. The innovation combines functional sports clothing with smart features that are not common until now and that are highly increasing the safety of the person wearing the items.

When it comes to competitors, there are existing product that can somehow be compared to the function and featurewise to the ideas of the group. There are jackets for increasing visibility that are of bright colour and that have added reflectors.⁷ Furthermore there is a smart bikingjacket existing, that increases the safety of the biker by indicating intended directions by light. Furthermore that jacket has an integrated navigation for the biker.⁸

Under European market, there are existing only very few companies producing similar illuminative jackets. Most of them are used for very specific property i.e. just for illumination by optical glass fibers or illumination by LED but not with additional property. This would lead to provide competitive advantage for the product to the

⁵ Cf. (online): Pincrestfabrics (2020).

⁶ Cf. (online): Rouse (2019).

⁷ Cf. (online): Decathlon(2020).

⁸ Cf. (online): Juschkat (2018).

company. Following are the companies producing similar product and which are meant to be competitors:

NEMEN® (ITALY):

An Italian based clothing company Nemen, established in 2012 produces casual lighting jackets for winter. The company uses optical fibers to be woven within nylon and steel which is garmented beneath thin film for rain/water protection. The inner layer is coated with aluminum to reflect body heat. The jacket uses two Li-ion rechargeable batteries to light up the fibers battery backup of 8 hours. Proposed price for the jacket is \$3000 which is equivalent to 2654 Euro.⁹

RAYLIER (ITALY):

Raylier provides an LED installed leather jackets for bikers in Europe, USA and Canada. The Italian based company, Raylier was founded very recently in 2018. The jacket contains 12 seamlessly included LEDs in the front and back with 3 outside and 3 inside pockets. Detachable rechargeable batteries are used with washable electronics. The lightings on the back are monitored by the speed and braking system of the bike. The resulting jacket is abrasion, shattering and cutting resistant. The price is casted to be 595 Euro.¹⁰

All in all one can say, that there are companies that are also focussing on safety sports wear especially for bikers but that there is up to now no product existing that has comparable or the same features to what is planned for the product to be developed.

The target customers for this innovative product are mainly persons involved in running and biking. Concerning about gender, the jacket is meant to be unisex. Due to the use of electricity and 3-layer heavy garmenting, the product is strictly advised for use to those above 18 years old. One of the main advantages of this jacket is the use of synthetic fibers which can further be recycled and the sustainability can be maintained. Therefore, environmentally conscious customers would also be attracted by the product.

⁹ Cf. (online): Nemen (2020).

¹⁰ Cf. (online): Raylier (2020).

3. Cost calculation

3.1 Cost Calculation Jacket

Table 1: Cost Calculation Illuminative Jacket

1. Material cost						
part dimension (mxm)	2 m	2 m	4 m ²			
Nylon						
part dimension (mxm)	2 m	2 m	4 m ²			
Fleece						
fabric area weight Nylon		80 g/m ²				
fabric area weight Fleece		250 g/m ²				
yarn costs	Glassfiber	1,5 €/kg				
fabric weight/part		m ² x g	1320 g			
1.1 fabric costs/part			cost weight x	1,98	€/part	
sensor		1 piece				
sensor costs		10 €/part				
batterie pack		1 piece				
batterie pack costs		90 €/part				
loudspeaker		1 pieces				
loudspeaker costs		2,83 €/part				
1.2 technical components				102,83	€/part	
zipper		1 piece				
zipper costs		1,5 €/part				
elastic band Hood		0,5 m				
elastic band Hood costs		1,5 €/part				
1.3 Further components				3	€/part	
Sum of materials				107,81	€/part	
materials overhead		25%		26,9525	€/part	
Material costs				134,7625	€/part	
2. Labour costs						
serial production:		10000	parts/year			
Nylon fabric m2			4m2 / piece	40000 m ² / year		
Fleece fabric m2			4m2 / piece	40000 m ² / year		
1. weaving machine:	2m width	600 rpm	50 picks/cm			

weaving time 1:		600 rpm 50 picks/cm		12cm/min	
weaving time 2:				7,2 m/h	
productivity				14,4 m ² /h	
production/day		9h per shift		129,6 m ² /day	
production days				308,6 days	
2. weaving machine:	2m width	650 rpm 55 picks/cm			
weaving time 1:		650 rpm 55 picks/cm		11,8 cm/min	
weaving time 2:				7,08 m/h	
productivity				14,16 m ² /h	
production/day		9h per shift		127,44 m ² /day	
production days				313,87 days	
labour costs for 1 machine					
personal costs		40000 per/y for one person			
personal month costs		40000: 12 month			3333,3 Euro / month
a) weaving (4P when 2 are working on each machine)			4PM		
b) cutting			2PM		
c) sewing			4PM		
d) application of technologies			2PM		
labour costs		sum: 12 month			39999,6 Euro
labour costs per part					3,99 Euro/part
overhead labour costs		50%			1,995 Euro/part
personal costs					5,985 Euro/part
3. Finishing costs					
Finishing costs-based on weight			13 Euro/kg		
weight of one part			1320g		
finishing of one part					17,16 Euro/part
Manufacturing costs (material+labour+finishing)					157,9075 Euro/part
overhead research & development (20 %)					31,58 Euro/part
overhead marketing (30%)					47,37 Euro/part
overhead administration (40%)					63,16 Euro/part
sum of overhead (=contribution margin)					142,11 Euro /part
cost price					300,01 Euro/part

The cost calculation for the smart biking jacket results in a **total cost price of 300,01 Euro/part.**

3.2 Cost Calculation Trousers

Table 2: Cost Calculation Illuminative Trousers

1. Material cost						
part dimension (mxm) Nylon	1,5	m	2	m	3	m ²
fabric area weight Nylon			80	g/m ²		
yarn costs	Glassfiber		1,5	€/kg		
fabric weight/part				m ² x g	240	g
1.1 fabric costs/part				cost x weight	0,36	€/part
sensor			1	piece		
sensor costs			10	€/part		
batterie pack			1	piece		
batterie pack costs			90	€/part		
loudspeaker			1	piece		
loudspeaker costs			2,83	€/part		
1.2 technical components					102,83	€/part
zipper			1	piece		
zipper costs			1	€/part		
stud			1	piece		
stud costs			0,65	€/part		
1.3 Further components					1,65	€/part
Sum of materials					104,84	€/part
materials overhead			25%		26,21	€/part
Material costs					131,05	€/part
2. Labour costs						
serial production:			10000 parts/year			
fabric m2				3m ² /piece	30000m ² /y	
weaving machine:	2m width	600 rpm 50 picks/cm				
weaving time 1:		600 rpm 50 picks/cm			12cm/min	
weaving time 2:					7,2m/h	
productivity					14,4m ² /h	
production/day		9h per shift			129,6 m ² /day	
production days					231,5 days	
labour costs for 1 machine						
personal costs		40000 per/y for one person				
personal month costs		40000 : 12 month			3333,3 Euro / month	

a) weaving			2PM			
b) cutting			2PM			
c) sewing			4PM			
d) application of technologies			2PM			
labour costs		sum: 10 month			33333 Euro	
labour costs per part					3,33 Euro/part	
overhead labour costs		50%			1,665 Euro/part	
personal costs					4,995 Euro/part	
3. Finishing costs						
Finishing costs-based on weight			13 Euro/kg			
weight of one part			240g			
finishing of one part					3,12 Euro/part	
Manufacturing costs (material+labour+finishing)					139,165 Euro/part	
overhead research & development (20%)					27,833 Euro/part	
overhead marketing (30%)					41,7495 Euro/part	
overhead administration (40%)					55,66 Euro/part	
sum of overhead (=contribution margin)					125,25 Euro/part	
cost price					264,41 Euro/part	

The cost calculation for the smart biking trousers results in a **total cost price of 300,01 Eurp/part.**

4. Idea Screening

4.1 Idea Screening Jacket

The following shows the idea screening for the smart biking jacket.

Table 3: Idea Screening Biking Jacket

New product success factors	(A) Relative importance	(B) Fit between product idea and company capabilities											Idea rating (AxB)	
		0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.10		
Market Chances	0,15			➡			+							0,075
Financial Resources	0,1			➡	+									0,03
Research and development	0,1					➡						+		0,09
development speed	0,07				➡	+								0,028
Technology/Innovation level	0,2							➡				+		0,18
potential growth	0,1					➡					+			0,07
competative advantage	0,1					➡					+			0,07
attractivity/satisfaction	0,1					➡					+			0,08
Distributions Channels	0,08		➡		+									0,024
Total	1													0,647

➡ Minimum value

The idea screening for the smart biking jacket results in a **total quality value of 0,647**.

4.2 Idea Screening Trousers

The following shows the idea screening for the smart biking trousers.

Table 4: Idea Screening Biking Trousers

New product success factors	(A) Relative importance	(B) Fit between product idea and company capabilities											Idea rating (AxB)	
		0.0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.10		
Market Chances	0,15			➡		+								0,06
Financial Resources	0,1			➡	+									0,03
Research and development	0,1					➡						+		0,09
development speed	0,07				➡	+								0,028
Technology/Innovation level	0,2							➡				+		0,18
potential growth	0,1					➡	+							0,05
competative advantage	0,1					➡					+			0,07
customer attractivity/satisfaction	0,1					➡	+							0,05
Distributions Channels	0,08		➡		+									0,024
Total	1													0,582

➡ Minimum value

The idea screening for the smart biking trousers results in a **total quality value of 0,582**.

5. Conceptual Design

The following chapter describes the product design of the prototype that we selected. The idea screening clarifies our vision of the choice of our product, i.e., “Illuminative Jacket”. The jacket was chosen as preference due to its higher **total quality value of 0,647** compared to the trousers with a **total quality value of 0,582**. Eventhough the **total cost price per part of the jacket is 35,60 Euro more expensive** than the total cost price of the trousers, the decision of choosing the illuminative jacket is justifiable with the higher quality value.

During the design we focused on the integration of functional requirements and wearing comfort. In the conceptual design step, we will discuss about all the possibilities to make our product with the help of subtasks and rate them by importance. We will consider the highest technology and lowest cost-effective option and also the highest cost effective and lowest technology as options for manufacturing of the product in the best possible way.

The ideas are based on the following success factors:

- a) **Raw Material:** For the manufacturing of our product, selection of potential raw material is very crucial. So, the relative importance of this sub-task was rated with 0.25 points keeping its importance in mind. Besides, functional importance and the surface feel both are important during the choice of raw material.
- b) **Fabric type:** The next important sub-task after the selection of the raw material was the fabric type. The right fabric type has a big impact on the physical properties of the jacket, so its relative importance was rated with 0.15 points.
- c) **Manufacturing process:** The next task was to select the process of manufacturing of the end product and the relative importance of this sub-task was given 0.1 points.
- d) **Illumination Technology:** We rated the illumination technology with 0.2 points as it was one of the two main functions to be added to our product.

- e) **Sensor type:** There are different options to detect any object near the jacket and the best possible options were cited. The relative importance of this sub-task was given 0.2 points as it was the second important function of the jacket.
- f) **Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish:** Different finishing could be applied to the jacket to improve its performance. Being a high-end product, it must have desirable smart properties to act as water barrier. As this property is very crucial for our product, so it was given 0.1 point.

Table 5: Conceptual design

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks			
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester	Cotton	Cotton+Polyester	Nylon+Fleece
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven	Non-woven	Warp knitted	Weft knitted
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring	Semi-automated tailoring	Adhesives	Welding
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED	LED	Electroluminescent fibres	Electroluminescent painted light paper
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor	Optical proximity sensor	Ultrasonic proximity sensor	Capacitive proximity sensor
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup	Carbon nanotubes	Hydrophobin SC3	Colloidal Silica
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D

Observation:

- a) **Raw Material:** We have identified raw materials like polyester, cotton, cotton/polyester blend and nylon with fleece as different raw materials impart different function to the end product.
- b) **Fabric type:** Keeping the structure, outlook and physical properties of the fabric in mind woven, non-woven, warp knit, and weft knit were identified as the possible fabric types.
- c) **Manufacturing process:** Different manufacturing processes can be used to produce the required end product and here we have identified tailoring, semi-automated tailoring, adhesives and welding as the possible options.

- d) **Illumination Technology:** Main function of our light up jacket is to illuminate itself and that is why we decided to select the best solution for our product among PLED, LED, Electroluminescent fibres and Electroluminescent painted light paper.
- e) **Sensor type:** The sensor is the second important function of the jacket which warns the wearer about the closing distance of any vehicle and to do the task Inductive proximity sensor, Optical proximity sensor, Ultrasonic proximity sensor and Capacitive proximity sensor were identified as the options.
- f) **Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish:** A suitable finishing was required for our light up jacket to enhance its performance and to add value to the product. The most important finish for our product is water repellency, which is why, hydrophobic finish and the relevant options were focused.

6. Rating Factors for each principle solution

6.1 Technology Rating

The following table illustrates the importance of the performance of the materials and processes where 1 is the best and 0 the worst:

Table 6: Technology Rating

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks			
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester 0.4	Cotton 0.1	Cotton+Polyester 0.3	Nylon+Fleece 0.7
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven 0.9	Non-woven 0.4	Warp knitted 0.6	Weft knitted 0.5
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring 0.7	Semi-automated tailoring 0.9	Adhesives 0.3	Welding 0.4
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED 0.7	LED 0.6	Electroluminescent fibres 0.9	Electroluminescent painted light paper 0.4
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor 0.4	Optical proximity sensor 0.9	Ultrasonic proximity sensor 0.3	Capacitive proximity sensor 0.7
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup 0.9	Carbon nanotubes 0.7	Hydrophobin SC3 0.4	Colloidal Silica 0.6
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D

Observation:

- a) **Raw Material:** Here, Nylon/Fleece blend is rated with the highest points as Nylon has higher strength, elasticity (even stronger than polyester), excellent toughness, abrasion resistance, easy cleanability, dye in wide range of colours, provides a smooth, soft and light weight fabric with high resilience. On the other hand, Fleece provides optimum warmth. Here, Cotton has got the lowest ratings because of the higher possibility to absorb water melt from snow.
- b) **Fabric type:** The woven fabric type is rated with the highest points because of its higher strength, stiffness, abrasion resistance and tightness compared to the other fabric types. The ratings of the warp and weft knitting are lower than woven. Because warp knitting cannot give structures like woven fabric and a bit more difficult to process, but it is versatile. On the other hand, weft knitting (circular) is not as versatile & of as high quality like woven and warp knitted fabric. The lowest rating is given to non-woven, because its strength is not comparable to the previous three options.
- c) **Manufacturing process:** Semi-automated tailoring got the highest rating because of having higher efficiency along with optimum production speed. Tailoring is also a good way to manufacture a product, but its efficiency is not as high as semi-automated one. Welding can also be a good way to create seams, but it will affect the appearance and physical properties of the product. The adhesive is rated with the lowest points as it cannot provide the seams the required strength.
- d) **Illumination Technology:** The rating of the Electroluminescent fibre is the highest because of high stretchability, decent light emitting performance with excellent stability than the other options. PLED, LED and Electroluminescent painted paper are also good options for our product, but these are technologically not so advanced like Electroluminescent fibres.
- e) **Sensor Type:** Because of having advantages like heat-free lighting, electrical safety, precise spotlighting, durability, easy to fabricate, less fragile, low voltage source, simpler installation and easy maintenance Optical proximity sensor is rated with the highest points.

- f) **Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish:** Hydrophobicity increases with the static contact angle of water with the surface. As the static contact angle of water with the surface for PAMAM dendrimer 5G is higher than the other options, so here PAMAM dendrimer has got the highest technological rating.¹¹

6.2 Cost Rating

The following table reflects the rating details considering the cost of the material/technology. Here, the highest rating is given to the option with the lowest cost.

Table 7: Cost Rating

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks			
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester 0.7	Cotton 0.8	Cotton+Polyester 0.9	Nylon+Fleece 0.5
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven 0.3	Non-woven 0.8	Warp knitted 0.6	Weft knitted 0.4
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring 0.5	Semi-automated tailoring 0.7	Adhesives 0.9	Welding 0.8
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED 0.6	LED 0.9	Electroluminescent fibres 0.3	Electroluminescent painted light paper 0.7
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor 0.9	Optical proximity sensor 0.8	Ultrasonic proximity sensor 0.3	Capacitive proximity sensor 0.6
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup 0.7	Carbon nanotubes 0.9	Hydrophobin SC3 0.5	Colloidal Silica 0.8
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D

Observation:

- a) **Raw Material:** Cotton/Polyester blend has got the highest rating because of having the lowest cost (0.77 €/ Kg)¹² than the other options. On the other hand, Nylon is rated with the lowest points because of the highest cost (2.70 €/ Kg)¹³. The rating of cotton and polyester are in-between these two and are 1.12 €/ Kg¹⁴ 1.24 €/ Kg¹⁵ respectively.

¹¹ Cf. Mahltig (2014), p.408.

¹² Cf. online: Alibaba (2020a).

¹³ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020b).

¹⁴ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020c).

¹⁵ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020d).

- b) **Fabric type:** Since the productivity of non-woven fabric is high, so cost of non-woven fabric is low which results in the highest cost rating of non-woven. On the other hand, since productivity of woven fabric is low, therefore price is high, thus cost rating is low for woven. Warp and weft knitting have got the in-between cost rating because of their moderate production speed and costing.
- c) **Manufacturing process:** The production/ assembling of a product with adhesives will cost lower than welding and semi-automated tailoring, that is why cost rating is the highest for adhesives. On the other hand, the costing per product will be the highest for tailoring process, so that tailoring gets the lowest rating points.
- d) **Illumination Technology:** The lowest cost of LED which is 1.36 €/piece makes it eligible for the highest cost rating. On contrary, the cost of Electroluminescent fibre is given the lowest rating because of its highest price. Electroluminescent painted light paper and PLED cost 4.16 €/piece¹⁶ and 17.97 €/piece¹⁷ respectively. So, these options are rated in-between the highest and lowest ratings.
- e) **Sensor type:** The cost of inductive proximity sensor is 4.50€/piece¹⁸, optical proximity sensor is 6.29 €/piece¹⁹, capacitive and ultrasonic proximity sensors are 8.63 €/piece²⁰ and 10.79 €/piece²¹. Thus, inductive proximity sensor and ultrasonic proximity sensor are rated with the highest and lowest points respectively.

Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish: Hydrophobin is rated the lowest because of its higher price which is 545 €/kg²². On the other hand, the highest rating is given to carbon nanotube because of its lowest price which is 2.6 €/kg²³. The price of Sol-gel products and Dendrimer Products are 20-31 €/kg²⁴ and 51 €/kg²⁵ respectively and these chemicals are rated in-between the highest and lowest rating points due to that reason.

¹⁶ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020g).

¹⁷ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020f).

¹⁸ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020j).

¹⁹ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020k).

²⁰ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020i).

²¹ Cf. online: Alibaba (2020l).

²² Cf. Mahltig (2014), p.408.

²³ Cf. Mahltig (2014), p.408.

²⁴ Cf. Mahltig (2014), p.408.

²⁵ Cf. Mahltig (2014), p.408.

7. Selection of Solution Combination

The following process after the valuations of the technology and the costs of the processes and materials is done by finding a suitable combination which will balance the best technology with the lowest cost of processes and materials.

Table 8: Technology rating for suitable combination with the best technology

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks				Sum HT	Sum LC
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester 0.4	Cotton 0.1	Cotton+Polyester 0.3	Nylon+Fleece 0.7	0.18	0.08
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven 0.9	Non-woven 0.4	Warp knitted 0.6	Weft knitted 0.5	0.14	0.06
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring 0.7	Semi-automated tailoring 0.9	Adhesives 0.3	Welding 0.4	0.09	0.03
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED 0.7	LED 0.6	Electroluminescent fibres 0.9	Electroluminescent painted light paper 0.4	0.18	0.12
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor 0.4	Optical proximity sensor 0.9	Ultrasonic proximity sensor 0.3	Capacitive proximity sensor 0.7	0.18	0.08
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup 0.9	Carbon nanotubes 0.7	Hydrophobin SC3 0.4	Colloidal Silica 0.6	0.09	0.07
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D	0.85	0.44

Table 9: Cost rating for suitable solution for a cost-effective combination

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks				Sum LC	Sum HT
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester 0.7	Cotton 0.8	Cotton+Polyester 0.9	Nylon+Fleece 0.5	0.23	0.13
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven 0.3	Non-woven 0.8	Warp knitted 0.6	Weft knitted 0.4	0.12	0.05
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring 0.5	Semi-automated tailoring 0.7	Adhesives 0.9	Welding 0.8	0.09	0.07
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED 0.6	LED 0.9	Electroluminescent fibres 0.3	Electroluminescent painted light paper 0.7	0.18	0.06
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor 0.9	Optical proximity sensor 0.8	Ultrasonic proximity sensor 0.3	Capacitive proximity sensor 0.6	0.18	0.16
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup 0.7	Carbon nanotubes 0.9	Hydrophobin SC3 0.5	Colloidal Silica 0.8	0.09	0.07
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D	0.89	0.53

HT= Highest technology product

LC= Low-cost product

Combination for the highest quality product= **D-A-B-C-B-A**

Combination for the low-cost product= **C-B-C-B-A-B**

In the following overview the quantitative results of the product with the highest quality and the product with the lowest costs are presented.

Table 10: Calculation of evaluation values

Solution Combination No. 01	Solution Combination No. 02
Highest Quality Product	Low Cost Product
D-A-B-C-B-A	C-B-C-B-A-B
0.85	0.44
0.53	0.89
1.38	1.33

The result of 1.38 represents the value of the highest quality product. That means that this product is 138% effective. In comparison, the product with low-cost is 133% effective. This finding already shows us that there is almost no decisive difference between these two options.

8. Final Decision

To decide which product solution is the most effective one, it is necessary to find a compromise between the product with the highest technology and the product with the lowest costs.

Table 11: Technology rating of selected solution for the final product

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks				Sum HT
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester	Cotton	Cotton+Polyester	Nylon+Fleece	0.18
		0.4	0.1	0.3	0.7	
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven	Non-woven	Warp knitted	Weft knitted	0.14
		0.9	0.4	0.6	0.5	
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring	Semi-automated tailoring	Adhesives	Welding	0.09
		0.7	0.9	0.3	0.4	
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED	LED	Electroluminescent fibres	Electroluminescent painted light paper	0.12
		0.7	0.6	0.9	0.4	
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor	Optical proximity sensor	Ultrasonic proximity sensor	Capacitive proximity sensor	0.18
		0.4	0.9	0.3	0.7	
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup	Carbon nanotubes	Hydrophobin SC3	Colloidal Silica	0.07
		0.9	0.7	0.4	0.6	
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D	0.77

Table 12: Cost rating of selected solution for the final product

Sub-tasks	Rel. imp.	Solution principles to sub-tasks				Sum LC
Raw Material	0.25	Polyester	Cotton	Cotton+Polyester	Nylon+Fleece	0.13
		0.7	0.8	0.9	0.5	
Fabric Type	0.15	Woven	Non-woven	Warp knitted	Weft knitted	0.05
		0.3	0.8	0.6	0.4	
Manufacturing Process	0.1	Tailoring	Semi-automated tailoring	Adhesives	Welding	0.07
		0.5	0.7	0.9	0.8	
Illumination Technology	0.2	PLED	LED	Electroluminescent fibres	Electroluminescent painted light paper	0.18
		0.6	0.9	0.3	0.7	
Sensor Type	0.2	Inductive proximity sensor	Optical proximity sensor	Ultrasonic proximity sensor	Capacitive proximity sensor	0.16
		0.9	0.8	0.3	0.6	
Chemicals for Hydrophobic finish	0.1	PAMAM dendrimer 5G, amino endgroup	Carbon nanotubes	Hydrophobin SC3	Colloidal Silica	0.09
		0.7	0.9	0.5	0.8	
Sum:	1	A	B	C	D	0.67

$$\text{Technology} + \text{Cost (final product)} = D - A - C - C - C - C = 0.77 + 0.67 = 1.44$$

The selected combination can be seen above. This compromise between the **high technology** and the **low-cost solution** has the rating of **1.44**, i.e. **144% efficiency**. It is the most effective way to achieve the product, which convinces with its technology and its price

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III. Appendix

Meeting participation list

The green coloured areas mark the attendance of each group member on the given date.

Name	Mat. No.	29.04.20	06.05.20	13.05.20	27.05.20	03.06.20	10.06.20	01.07.20	15.07.20	29.07.20	12.08.20	02.09.20
Milena Blessin	1029457											
Laura Juchem	1300637											
Dhruv Ramani	1312704											
Md. Salauddin Sikder	1311187											
Md. Zulifikar Hasan	1323465											

Tasks and responsible group members

Work step / task	Responsible group member	Comment
Cost Calculation	Laura, Milena	Cost Calculation with goal of cost price of both products
Idea Screening	Laura	Idea Screening with goal of total quality value of both products
Product explanation	Milena	Description of selected field and innovation
Conceptual Design	Zulifikar, Salauddin, Dhruv	possibilities to make product with the help of subtasks and rate them by importance
Rating Factors for each principle solution	Zulifikar, Salauddin, Dhruv	Importance of performance of materials and processes
Selection of Solution Combination	Zulifikar, Salauddin, Dhruv	Selection of Solution Combinatio
Final Decision	Zulifikar, Salauddin, Dhruv	Decision on which solution is most effective
Final Report	Milena	Writing the report and collecting all results
Final Report revision	Laura	Finishing Report, final revision, formal matters

Meeting Reports

Meeting Date	Participants	Outcomes
29.04.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	Collecting first ideas on the product field and on suitable materials for the innovation
06.05.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	The decision on two products and their details that are taken as objects of the decision was made, tasks were aligned to group members
13.05.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin	The outcomes of the cost calculation were discussed and adjustments were made
27.05.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	The product explanation was discussed and the ways of processing for the conceptual design were reviewed as a group
03.06.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	The students working on the conceptual design, rating and the selection of solution combinations informed the others about the status.
10.06.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	The students working on the conceptual design, rating and the selection of solution combinations informed the others about the status
01.07.20	Laura, Dhruv, Zulfikar	The students working on the conceptual design, rating and the selection of solution combinations informed the others about the status. Adjustments were made
15.07.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	The final decision was discussed in plenum
29.07.20	Milena, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	Collecting all parts of the report
12.08.20	Milena, Laura, Salauddin, Zulfikar	Discussing some slight adjustments on the report
02.09.20	Milena, Laura, Dhruv, Salauddin, Zulfikar	Last meet-up before submission, answering some last questions

IV. Statements

We herewith declare that we have completed the report by ourselves and without the use of any aids other than those listed.

All passages that were taken either literally or analogously from published and unpublished sources, have been marked as such. The report has never been submitted to a different examination authority in the same or similar form.

Mönchengladbach, 02/09/2020

Location and Date

Md Salauddin Sikder

Student Name

Signature

Aachen, 02/09/2020

Location and Date

Laura Juchem

Student Name

Signature

|

Gujarat, India | 02/09/2020

Location and Date

Dhruv Ramani

Student Name

Signature

Mönchengladbach, 02.09.2020

Location and Date

Md. Zulfikar Hasan

Student Name

Zulfikar

Signature

Aachen, 29.8.20

Location and Date

Milena Blessin

Student Name

Blessin

Signature